

Sharia Rules Regarding Halal Food

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Abstract

Diet is the apparent survival of human being, as well as the basic and fundamental need of every human being. It recognized that food has most important in any human life. The physical protection of mental and spiritual health is based on human diet. The effects of diet are on both private and public aspects of human life. The performance of good and evil in life is also related to diet. If the food is pure the person himself, the pure, and the attributes of the person become a useful part of the society for others, so that the world also becomes a path of good and hereafter. If the diet is unclean, the actions that are released from the human body are bad, and such a person, for himself and especially for religion, Islam is the basic unit of life. Therefore, Islam has emphasized a lot of food, Islam only corrects pure things for humans and prevents the use of dirty and unclean things. It is in the Quran: "people ask you what things are lawful for them"? Say unto you that all pure things are lawful for them. In the second place, "all pure things are lawful for them, and all dirty things are forbidden." the summary of religious orders is to adopt two things lawful and to take away from committing haram. If the summary of the whole religion is permissible, then it is permissible for them to do so. There are effects of forbidden food that are coming in front of time, every human is seeking paradise, and the way the person wears paradise.

Keywords: Halal Food, Halal Industry, Shariah Accreditation, Sharia Rules, Forbidden Food

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